

Table 2. Percent blast disease index (PDI) and percent neck blast incidence (%).^a

Variety	Leaf color chart value (%) ^b					Recommended practice	Mean
	2.0	2.75	3.5	4.25	5.0		
<i>Leaf blast incidence</i>							
<i>1998</i>							
Abhilash	12.7 b x	15.2 b wx	17.4 b w	21.4 b v	23.3 b v	17.1 b w	17.9 b 36.3 a
Intan	30.6 a w	31.9 a w	34.0 a w	39.7 a v	42.1 a v	39.3 a v	
Mean	21.6 y	23.6 wx	25.7 x	30.5 v w	32.7 v	28.2 y	
<i>1999</i>							
Intan	17.5 y	20.8 xy	21.4 wx	24.4 w	30.1 v	23.3 wx	0
Abhilash	0	0	0	0	0	0	
<i>Neck blast incidence</i>							
<i>1998</i>							
Abhilash	16.1 b y	21.7 b x	27.4 b w	29.2 b w	34.8 b v	28.0 b w	26.2 b 32.2 a
Intan	22.5 a y	29.2 a x	34.0 a w	36.3 a w	40.7 a v	36.4 a w	
Mean	19.3 y	25.5 x	30.8 w	32.8 w	37.7 v	32.2 w	
<i>1999</i>							
Abhilash	18.0 a v	20.5 a v	21.2 b v	21.4 b v	21.5 b v	20.6 b v	20.6 b 27.0 a
Intan	18.0 a z	21.6 a yz	25.0 a xy	32.2 a vw	37.0 a v	27.4 a xy	
Mean	18.0 y	21.1 xy	23.2 x	26.8 vw	29.3 v	24.8 wx	

^aDuncan's multiple range test (DMRT at 5%) was used to compare treatment means. ^bRows/columns followed by the same letters do not differ significantly; comparison of means in a row is indicated by a to e and comparison of means in a column by v to z.

Table 3. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹), 1998.^a

Variety	Leaf color chart treatment ^b					Recommended practice	Mean
	2.0	2.75	3.5	4.25	5.0		
Abhilash	c	c	b	a	a	bc	4.2 a
	3.3 a x	3.1 a x	4.3 a w	5.2 a v	5.5 a v	4.0 a wx	
Intan	b	b	a	b	b	b	3.0 a
	2.9 a w	2.9 a w	4.4 a v	2.5 b w	2.2 b w	2.8 a w	
Mean	b	b	a	ab	ab	b	
	3.1 w	3.0 w	4.4 v	3.9 vw	3.8 vw	3.4 w	

^aDuncan's multiple range test (DMRT) at 5% was used to compare treatment means. ^bRows/columns followed by the same letters do not differ significantly.

cation of 170 kg ha⁻¹. Grain yields in these treatments were significantly higher than those under recommended N management (Table 3).

Results indicated that N application based on an LCC value of 3.5 helped to manage blast more effectively in a susceptible variety (Intan) compared with the recommended practice of N application. Rice productivity can be increased by higher N application based on the LCC reading. The critical LCC value for N management varied between the two varieties.

Reference

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Water and weed management studies in direct-seeded upland rice

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Direct-seeded upland rice is an important system of rice culture occupying almost 22% of the total rice area in India. In Assam, this crop is locally known as *ahu* rice (Mar/Apr–Jun/July). Assam farmers prefer this crop because this period is characterized by low rainfall, clear skies, and low frequency of floods. However, some constraints limit the widespread cultivation of *ahu* rice:

uncertain rainfall; high evaporative demand, causing moisture stress; and weed infestation. Although the application of irrigation can solve the problem of moisture stress, scheduling of irrigation in upland situations where seed is sown in dry unpuddled soil is very difficult. Hence, upland rice should have drought tolerance to withstand possible moisture stress in be-

tween irrigation schedules. Seed hardening with potassium salt before sowing helps induce drought tolerance in crops (Chinoy et al 1970).

This study was carried out to assess the performance of upland rice under seed treatment and water and weed management practices. The experiment was conducted at AAU during the 1991 summer (Mar-Jul) in a

randomized block design with three replications (net plot size, 4.5 × 3.0 m) using rice cv IR50, which is recommended for the ahu season. Three factors were studied: (1) seed treatment (normal practice: without seed soaking and application of recommended 16.6 kg K ha⁻¹; modified practice: seed soaking in 40% KCl solution, application of 49.8 kg K ha⁻¹; and 50 ppm paraquat spraying at tillering stage); (2) water management practices (rainfed, intermittent irrigation at 3 d and 6 d); and (3) weed control measures (weedy check and application of butachlor at 2 kg ai ha⁻¹): plots were surrounded by dikes and irrigation was applied by flash flooding the plots and bringing the soil water content to field capacity. The weedy check plot had no weed control, except for one manual weeding 15 d after sowing. The soil type was sandy loam with pH 4.29, 0.72% organic carbon, and 274 kg available N ha⁻¹, 3 kg P ha⁻¹, and 77 kg K ha⁻¹. Seeds were sown on 15 March and harvested on 15 July 1991. Before sowing, 10 t farmyard manure ha⁻¹, 40 kg N ha⁻¹, and 20 kg P ha⁻¹ were uniformly applied. The differential levels of K were

applied in two equal splits—at tillering and at panicle initiation. Seed soaking was combined with a higher K dose to induce drought tolerance where K could help a lot. The rainfall received during the crop growth period was 975 mm.

Water productivity was calculated as grain yield divided by consumptive use. Consumptive use was worked out based on moisture depletion from the root zone, rainfall received during crop growth, and irrigation water applied. Soil water content was measured by the volumetric method. Irrigation water was applied on a per-volume basis, providing a 5-cm depth each time. The required volume was divided by the discharge rate to find the time needed for irrigating the plot. Root volume per plant was measured by the volume displacement method (Mishra and Ahmed 1987). Weed dry matter was measured from a 0.5-m² sample area, with three samples per plot.

Results of the experiment showed that the modified seed treatment significantly increased the number of effective tillers and root volume compared with the

normal practice, although there was no significant difference in yield (Table 1).

The 3-d intermittent irrigation resulted in a significant increase in root volume over the rainfed treatment. Water productivity was higher under the rainfed condition, followed by intermittent irrigation at 6 d. This may be due to the equal distribution of rainfall during the crop season.

In the weed control treatment, butachlor significantly increased the number of effective tillers, number of grain panicles, and grain yield over the weedy check (Table 1). Applying butachlor increased yield by 23% over the weedy check. Mishra et al (1988) and Singh and Bhattacharjee (1989) reported similar beneficial effects of butachlor in upland rice. Water productivity in the butachlor plots was greater than in the weedy check because of higher yield. The application of butachlor significantly reduced the dry matter weight of grassy weeds at all stages of observation (Table 2).

Presowing seed with 4% KCl combined with 49.8 kg K ha⁻¹ and 50 ppm paraquat spray-

Table 1. Influence of seed treatment, water management, and weed control measures on yield components, grain yield, root volume, and water productivity of direct-seeded upland rice.

Treatment ^a	Effective tillers m ⁻² (no.)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Root volume (cm ³ plant ⁻¹)	Consumptive water use (cm)	Water productivity (kg ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)
Seed							
Normal	100	78	20.5	2.4	21.0	115	21
Modified	120	78	20.7	2.6	25.0	112	23
CD (0.05)	5	ns	ns	ns	3.4	–	–
Water management							
Rainfed	107	80	21.0	2.4	20.6	81	30
3 DII	113	77	20.6	2.6	26.5	139	18
6 DII	111	77	20.5	2.5	23.0	119	21
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	4.2	–	–
Weed control							
Weedy check	90	74	77.0	2.2	23.0	113	20
Butachlor at 2 kg ai ha ⁻¹	130	82	78.0	2.8	23.5	114	24
CD (0.05)	5.5	3.7	ns	0.2	ns	–	–

^aDII = days of intermittent irrigation; ns = not significant.

ing at tillering could give the crop protection against drought. Applying butachlor considerably reduced weed pressure.

References

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Table 2. Influence of seed treatment, water management, and weed control measures on weed dry matter (g m^{-2}).^a

Treatment	30 DAS		60 DAS		Harvest	
	Grass	Nongrass	Grass	Nongrass	Grass	Nongrass
Seed						
Normal	53	5	54	21	99 (8) ^b	45 (6)
Modified	43	7	48	15	101 (9)	99 (6)
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	5	ns	ns
Water management						
Rainfed	58	5	48	18	110 (9)	46 (5)
3 DII	44	5	53	20	99 (9)	57 (6)
6 DII	45	6	33	17	90 (8)	62 (6)
CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Weed control						
Weedy check	68	6	66	16	140 (11)	23 (5)
Butachlor at 2 kg ai ha ⁻¹)	30	5	39	20	59 (6)	60 (7)
CD (0.05)	14	ns	9	5	3	ns

^aDAS = days after sowing, ns = not significant, DII = days of intermittent irrigation. ^bNumbers in parentheses are square-root-transformed values.

Effect of organic matter resources and inorganic fertilizers on yield and nutrient uptake in the rice-wheat cropping system

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A field experiment was conducted at the Fertilizer Research Station, Pura, Kanpur (India), during 1997-98 and 1998-99 to study the influence of organic sources along with inorganic fertilizers on the rice-wheat cropping system. The soil had the following characteristics: sand 51.8%, silt 25.6%, clay 21.3%, pH 7.9, electrical conductivity (EC, dS m⁻¹) 0.39, organic carbon 4.3 g kg⁻¹, available N 163.2 kg ha⁻¹, 7.1 kg P ha⁻¹, and 103.8 kg K ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design consisting of five main-plot treatments: M₁—green manure (*Sesbania aculeata*), M₂—moong legume (*Phaseolus aureus*)

straw (5 t ha⁻¹), M₃—farmyard manure (5 t ha⁻¹), M₄—rice straw (5 t ha⁻¹), and M₅—weedy fallow; and five subplot treatments: F₀—control, F₁—50% N, F₂—50% NP, F₃—50% NPK, and F₄—100% NPK of the recommended dose (120 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 49.8 kg K).

Adding different sources of organic matter significantly increased rice yield over weedy fallow. Treatments also differed significantly from each other. Maximum grain yield (3.7 t ha⁻¹) during 1997 and 1998 was obtained by M₁, followed by M₃ (3.6 t ha⁻¹), M₂ (3.5 t ha⁻¹), and M₄ (3.4 t ha⁻¹). Minimum grain yield was ob-

tained under the fallow treatment. Similarly, chemical fertilizers also significantly increased yield compared with the fertilizer control. A minimum yield of 2.0 t ha⁻¹ in the control increased to 3.2 t ha⁻¹ with F₁, to 3.6 t ha⁻¹ in F₂, to 4.0 t ha⁻¹ in F₃, and to 4.7 t ha⁻¹ in F₄ during 1997. A similar trend was recorded in 1998 (Table 1).

Different organic matter sources exhibited significant residual responses on grain and straw yield of the wheat crop. Maximum yield in the wheat crop was noted in the treatment with green manure, followed by farmyard manure, moong straw, and rice straw (Table 2).